

THE RIGHT TO HIGHER EDUCATION FROM A HUMAN RIGHTS PERSPECTIVE ON A FEDERAL INSTITUTE *CAMPUS*

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ABSTRACT

This paper briefly discusses the struggle for access to higher education for students who have historically been excluded from this level of education. These students come from the most sensitive social strata of Brazilian society. This population of students is more vulnerable due to their low family income, color, race and specific needs (people with some kind of disability). The aim is to ascertain the validity of the legislation in correcting this historical debt to this population of students, with regard to the right to higher education, on a federal institute *Campus*. At the same time, this right is based on human rights as one of the rights of the human being. The methodology used in this research has a mixed qualitative and quantitative approach, which includes document analysis and a search for data available from the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research - Anísio Teixeira - Inep. The results are promising and point to expected percentages of enrollment of students from the most vulnerable social classes at this level of education. They are evidence that the legislation in force, which ensures the democratization of access to higher education, has been effective in correcting inequality and inequity, although it needs to be updated.

Keywords: Right to Education. Human Rights. Higher Education. Quota students.

RESUMO

Neste artigo aborda-se, brevemente, a trajetória de luta do acesso à educação superior da população de estudantes que, historicamente, foi excluída desse nível de

ensino. Esses estudantes têm suas origens em camadas sociais mais sensíveis da sociedade brasileira. Essa população de estudantes é mais vulnerável em função da baixa renda familiar, cor, raça e necessidade específica (pessoa com algum tipo de deficiência). O objetivo consiste em averiguar a validade da legislação na correção dessa dívida histórica com essa população de estudantes, no que se refere ao direito à educação superior, em um Campus de instituto federal. Pautando, concomitantemente, esse direito com os direitos humanos como sendo um direito do ser humano. A metodologia utilizada nesta pesquisa possui uma abordagem mista, qualitativa e quantitativa, que inclui análise documental e busca de dados disponíveis pelo Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais – Anísio Teixeira – Inep. Os resultados são promissores e apontam percentuais esperados de matrículas de estudantes de classes sociais mais vulneráveis nesse nível de ensino. São evidências de que a legislação vigente que assegura a democratização do acesso à educação superior, tem sido eficiente na correção da desigualdade e da inequidade, embora careça de atualizações.

Palavras-chave: Direito a Educação. Direitos Humanos. Educação Superior. Estudantes Cotistas.

INTRODUCTION

With regard to Brazil, it is worth noting that the educational system was structured and expanded by the dominant class, formed by elite and white agents, who relied on the issue of meritocracy to control access to higher education, as if it were the only logical criterion for entry into this level of education (Ferraro, 2008).

Affirmative action was essential in the processes of access to higher education, and these actions have their origins in the "*igualdade formal que foi conquistada com as revoluções burguesas nos séculos XVII e XVIII, especificamente, a Revolução Inglesa, a Revolução Americana e a Revolução Francesa*"¹ (Silva Filho, 2014, p. 3).

In turn, these revolutions had their signatures on Human Rights, which were being constituted as tools of the struggle for social justice. These tools are sustained and act in actions that aim at the principles of equality and equity: "[...] *sem distinção de nação, raça, Estado, gênero, orientação sexual, etnia, condição física ou idade*"² (Silva Filho, 2014, p. 3).

It is accepted that this heritage of humanity has been built throughout history, through social movements. As a result, "*reivindicações e lutas fizeram avançar*

¹Free translation (Own). "Formal equality that was achieved with the bourgeois revolutions in the 17th and 18th centuries, specifically the English Revolution, the American Revolution and the French Revolution".

²Free translation (Own). "[...] without distinction of nation, race, state, gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, physical condition or age".

legislações, compreensões culturais sobre o que a sociedade considera justo, levando em consideração as configurações econômicas e territoriais dos povos”³ (Silva Filho, 2014, p. 3).

However, this was not enough to combat inequality, much less equity in education, given that there is a history of contradictions between the market and society that accumulate injustices over time. This fact ratifies the historical debt of access to education by disadvantaged groups.

In Brazil, this historical educational debt began to be traced and tackled in the 1988 Federal Constitution (CF/88) (Brasil, 1988). The Law of Guidelines and Bases of Education of December 20, 1996 (LDB/96) (Brasil, 1996) together with the CF/88 indicated in their texts that education should be provided respecting the principle of equal conditions for access and permanence in school. The readings, interpretations and studies of these texts served as a basis for the design of vacancy reservation policies, which were understood as initiatives to promote equality, reducing social and school injustices (Bayma, 2012).

In the early 2000s, the first steps were taken towards processes of democratization of access and permanence in higher education. In these initial processes, quotas were established for students from disadvantaged classes. As these processes were at the discretion of each Higher Education Institution (HEI) and, therefore, did not have a standardization, in 2012 Law No. 12,711 of August 29, 2012 (Brasil, 2012) was enacted, which regulated the method of distributing places in higher education for this population of students.

In these terms, it would be appropriate to question whether, after more than a decade, the legislative processes have corrected the historical debt with the population of students who were once excluded from higher education, having as study a federal institute *Campus*? In other words, through the current legislation, is the right to access, permanence and completion of higher education being guaranteed to these students?

Thereby, the aim of this study is to investigate the validity of the legislation in the correction of this historical debt with this population of students, on a federal institute *Campus*, with regard to the right to higher education. To this end, a methodology with a mixed approach, qualitative and quantitative, is used, which includes document analysis and search for quantitative data in the NIESR database.

³Free translation (Own). "Demands and struggles have advanced legislation, cultural understandings of what society considers fair, taking into account the economic and territorial configurations of peoples".

Thus, this paper is organized as follows: in addition to this introduction, four more sections have been developed. The first section presents the methodological procedures; the second section emphasizes the literature review on the legislative processes of the right to higher education in the country; the third section presents the analysis and discussion of the results; the fourth section presents the final considerations and, finally, the bibliographic references.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

For this study, an exploratory methodology was used. With a mixed, qualitative and quantitative approach. A collection of government documentation and papers was compiled. Documents from Official Institutions were consulted and interpreted, such as those of the NIESR, of the Ministry of Education (MEC) and the Federal Institute of Brasília (FIB).

Research qualitative is a systematic and subjective approach that explains daily life experiences by giving them meaning (Khan, 2014). This type of research allows researchers to explore in depth the behaviors, from different perspectives, life experiences to study the complexities of the situation through a defined framework of this qualitative method (Khan, 2014).

The quantitative methodology examines the constructs of association between variables that can be generalized to a population group through statistical inferences. In this methodology, data and information tend to be objective formats and can be collected in various ways and assume values in both quantitative and qualitative aspects (Galvão; Pluye; Ricarte, 2018).

Mixed methodology is a combination of quantitative methodology and qualitative methodology techniques, which address theories and language in a single survey. In these cases, qualitative findings need to be complemented with quantitative results. Therefore, these methodologies are complementary to each other (Jamshed, 2014).

In order to quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate public policies for access to higher education, through the inclusion of students who, for decades, were excluded from this level of education, the Taguatinga *Campus* was chosen at this Institute. This choice was due to the fact that it has undergraduate courses in the three types of offers: Licentiate, Technology and Bachelor's Degree. In addition to this factor, it is the one with the largest number of undergraduate courses at this Institute.

With the aim of to identify relevant reading results related to the Right to Education, Higher Education, Law of Access to Higher Education and Human Rights in Education, a combination of research strategies was used. These included: exploration and research through relevant work bases; verification of the reference list; citation search and other sources. Four databases were selected: Scielo; journal portal of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (Cihep); Elsevier and Science Direct, Education Resources Information Center (Eric).

The search in these databases allowed a review of the most recent academic content, as well as historical, specific and multidisciplinary content. Table 1 provides an overview of the screening and selection process of the evaluated works

Table 1 – Screening process of the references selected for the research

Screening and Selection of References				
Database	Right to Education	Higher Education	Higher Education and Human Rights in Education	Total works/titles
Scielo	15	22	28	65
Cihep Journals	12	24	35	71
Science Direct	8	4	9	21
Eric	5	8	4	17
Total	40	58	76	174

Source: prepared by the author (2024).

The bibliographic and documentary research was carried out from March 2024 to June 2024, comprising papers written between 2012 and 2024, with some publications related to the theme being admitted that were outside this period. A total of 174 papers were identified for the screening of titles, which were abstracts and bibliographic information. Based on this, the inclusion/exclusion criteria mentioned above were verified. After completion of this stage, 46 studies were classified.

At the end of this stage, 17 were excluded, as they did not meet the criteria established for this research. In view of the above, 29 papers were selected for thematic analysis. Official government documents available on portals, such as planalto.gov, mec.gov, which deal with Laws, Decrees, Resolutions, Norms and Guidelines, Institutional Programs and other normative acts, were analyzed. Chart 1 shows the criteria for how the papers were selected.

Chart 1 – Inclusion and exclusion criteria for selected papers

CRITERION - FOCUS		
Higher Education	Higher Education Access Policies	Language
Right to Education. Access to Higher Education. University Student Aid.	Human Rights in Education Educational Affirmative. Action Policies. Quota policies. Policies for Higher Education Students.	English. Spanish. Portuguese.

Source: prepared by the author (2024).

Certain criteria were established that met the prerogatives of this study, in order to guarantee a certain degree of quality and relevance of the papers selected. Papers were included in the analysis if their focus was on: Higher Education, Policies for Access to Higher Education, Right to Education. The population of interest was subjects related to Human Rights in Education, such as Educational Affirmative Action Policies, Quota Policies, Policies for Attention to Students in Higher Education, as well as subjects that referred to the Right of Access and Permanence of Quota Students in Higher Education; papers published in Spanish, English and Portuguese.

THE RIGHT TO HIGHER EDUCATION AS HUMAN RIGHT

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on December 10, 1948, attributing inherent and inalienable fundamental rights to every human being. These fundamental rights include, among others, that “everyone has the right to education [...] education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages and elementary education shall be compulsory” (United Nations, 1948, Art. 26). It is highlighted that “*Los Derechos Humanos corresponden al conjunto de los derechos individuales y colectivos inherentes a todas las personas sin distinción; son universales, inalienables, indivisibles e interdependientes*”⁴ (Oliva; Beltrán, 2020, p. 2).

Since, in an attempt to guarantee a person's right to education, the necessary conditions for access to education must be met. Thus, the enjoyment of the right to education by one person cannot interfere with the enjoyment of this right by others.

⁴Free translation (Own). Human Rights correspond to the whole of inherent individual and collective rights to all people without distinction; are universal, inalienable, indivisible and interdependent.

This is because the enjoyment of the right to education by one person cannot be interfered with by others (Lindahl, 2006).

For Nesseler (2023) the linguistic Human Rights have been defined as being “so fundamental that every individual has them because that individual is a human being, so inalienable that no state is allowed to violate them, and which are necessary for individuals and groups to live a dignified life” (Skutnabb-Kangas, 2018, p. 39). It is also noteworthy that “numerous authors have advocated that school and university science education should be based on an understanding of science education as a Human Right” (Schuck; Feser, 2022, p. 338).

Schuck and Feser (2022) recall that, on the other hand, Milner (2015) pointed out that since science education has the status of a type of education and, since education is a human right, it should also be considered a human right. It is appropriate to ascertain that linguistic Human Rights are related to education through the struggles of individuals who use minority languages. With this, their communities are engaged in this struggle to ensure and maintain survival and continuous development (Nesser, 2018). It is clear that “the recognition of the importance of human rights education for the implementation and for the respect of human rights has grown in the last years” (Tibbitts; Kirchsclaeger, 2010, p. 1).

Besides, it is possible to consider that “the Human Rights Education is an emergent field of educational theory and practice gaining increased attention and significance across the globe” (Tibbitts; Kirchsclaeger, 2010, p. 1). As a result, there was an organization in the international Human Rights movements of various entities, including the United Nations (UN), regional Human Rights bodies, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). This fact has led to the broadening of the focus of this theme and, thus, since 1970 there has been an attempt to integrate concepts, norms and values of Human Rights in the main educational systems of the countries (Tibbitts; Kirchsclaeger, 2010).

Nevertheless, two decades of the twenty-first century have passed and humanity still lives with the violation of basic rights, practically, in all countries, especially those where poverty is a mark that persists throughout their histories. Among these violated rights, the right to food, health, education, among others, can be mentioned. One of the direct implications of this violation of basic rights is the intensification of conflicts manifested in the increase in violence due to wars between nations. To justify attempts to solve these conflicts, they intensify military interventions,

which threatens Human Rights, in addition to other types of catastrophes (Acosta, 2018).

According to the author,

Por todo lo anterior se hace necesaria la educación para los Derechos Humanos. La Educación no es solo un derecho para todos, sino ella tiene por objeto el fortalecimiento de los Derechos Humanos. La educación ayuda a los seres humanos a ser autónomos, a tener mejor calidad de vida, a tomar decisiones, a ser solidarios. No solo se tiene derecho a acceder a la educación, sino acceder a una educación de calidad⁵ (Acosta, 2018, p. 161).

With regard to educational processes *“El derecho a la educación es un derecho humano reconocido [...] como también un acceso equitativo a la educación superior, y una responsabilidad de proveer educación básica a los individuos que no han completado la educación primaria”⁶ (Acosta, 2018, p. 162).* It is worth mentioning that the management of education looks beyond a set of quality indicators, which means that monitoring within the structures of Human Rights is also desired. This right is contained in several international Human Rights treaties (Acosta, 2018).

Attention is drawn to the fact that there is so much to be learned from the continuing violations of Human Rights obligations in schools and from the responses, or lack thereof, to the violation of rights and characteristics of an education that respects Human Rights (Lundy; Sainz, 2018).

According to Oliveira et al. (2022) in Brazil, the Federal Constitution of 1988, called the “Citizen Constitution”, brought in its text, an underlined mention of Human Rights. However, there has been no effective implementation of such rights in the national territory. From the understanding that Human Rights are fundamental to a society, establishing education in Human Rights enables the citizens of this society “to respect human beings, their dignity, democratic values, tolerance, and a harmonious coexistence according to the norms of the rule of law, contributing for the population’s taking a protagonist role in their history” (Oliveira et al., 2022, p. 2).

These authors understand that:

⁵Free translation (Own). For all of the above, education for human rights is necessary. Education is not only a right for all, but it aims to strengthen human rights. Education helps human beings to be autonomous, to have a better quality of life, to make decisions, to be supportive. Not only do you have the right to access education, but also to access quality education.

⁶Free translation (Own). “The right to education is a recognized human right [...] as well as equitable access to higher education, and a responsibility to provide basic education to individuals who have not completed primary education”.

Regarding Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), they have an evident duty to participate in the construction of a culture of HR promotion, protection, defense and repair through the inseparable principles of teaching, research and extension, aiming to train social agents committed to the future of society, with the goal of promoting development, social justice, democracy and peace (Oliveira et al., 2022, p. 2).

In this sense, “addressing Education in Human Rights in Brazil is one of the demands and urgencies to promote a more humane education and the empowerment of the democratic political regime in society” (Cordeiro; Souza; Costa, 2022, p. 12). Based on the opposition to meritocracy, it is understood that, “*no âmbito teórico-conceitual propôs-se uma noção de justiça social cuja amplitude incorporou a distribuição socioeconômica e o reconhecimento cultural. Analisou a construção da juridicidade da política de cotas como ampliação do direito à educação superior*”⁷ (Batista, 2018, p. 41).

It is understandable, therefore, that programs seek to promote the development of a plural, diverse, conscious, tolerant of differences and democratic society, since it would grant relevant spaces for minorities to participate in the community. With this, it is understood that compensatory justice, “[...] *está baseada na retificação de injustiças ou de falhas cometidas contra grupos no passado, ora por particulares, ora pelo governo, em relação aos membros de determinado grupo minoritário*”⁸ (Bayma, 2012, p. 330).

It was precisely on this basis that the first formulation of a bill with a view to affirmative action in Brazil, dating back to the 1980s, was made by the then federal deputy Abdias do Nascimento, the first black parliamentarian to defend proposals for the promotion of civil rights for the black population. The bill proposed compensatory action measures for black Brazilians (Figueiredo, 2022). In this project presented by the then deputy Abdias do Nascimento there were a series of measures that claimed the reservation of vacancies. Moehleck (2016) points out that this reservation system would take place by:

[...] *reserva de 20% de vagas para mulheres negras e 20% para homens negros na seleção de candidatos ao serviço público; bolsas*

⁷Free translation (Own). “In the theoretical-conceptual sphere, it proposed a notion of social justice whose scope incorporated socio-economic distribution and cultural recognition. It analyzed the construction of the legality of the quota policy as an extension of the right to higher education”.

⁸Free translation (Own). [...] it is based on the rectification of injustices or failures committed against groups in the past, sometimes by individuals, sometimes by the government, in relation to members of a certain minority group.

de estudos; incentivos às empresas do setor privado para a eliminação da prática da discriminação racial; incorporação da imagem positiva da família afro-brasileira ao sistema de ensino e à literatura didática e paradidática, bem como introdução da história das civilizações africanas e do africano no Brasil”⁹ (Moehlecke, 2016, p. 421).

From the perspective of this reflection, according to Batista (2018), it is possible to consider that quotas for higher education are legal instruments that seek to guarantee social rights to citizens who were once excluded from this level of education. On the other hand, the role of compensatory policies for the reduction of social inequality in countries that did not guarantee equal rights for citizenship is recognized, as is the case of Brazil (Batista, 2018).

Through these policies, it is possible to recognize the existence of social inequalities that need to be overcome in order to effectively promote social inclusion, increasing the representation of disadvantaged groups in society in general (Reis, 2022). It would then be *"por meio de ações compensatórias e redistributivas que compensem ou corrijam a discriminação que sofreram ao longo da vida. Partindo desse princípio, defende-se que não se pode atender de forma igual quem é diferente para não perpetuar as desigualdades"*¹⁰ (Reis, 2022, p. 111).

Therefore, “this conception of education that is sensitive to human rights recognizes difference as a notable characteristic of modern societies and, therefore, to its formative potential, while at the same, promotes equality in the context of educational experiences” (Cordeiro; Souza; Costa, 2022, p. 9). It can be seen, therefore, that in the face of differences, the struggle for equality continues today, without necessarily denying the relevance of this struggle. These differences caused political and epistemological changes in the conduct of life and society. Education must be understood as the vector for the construction of these differences, being the scenario of these epistemological changes. In this scenario lies the space for the realization of the posture in relation to social diversity (Cordeiro; Souza; Costa, 2022).

In Brazil, only in 2012, a fundamental milestone was instituted for quota policies through the approval of Law No. 12,711/2012. This Law was regulated by Decree No.

⁹Free translation (Own). [...] reservation of 20% of vacancies for black women and 20% for black men in the selection of candidates for public service; scholarships; incentives to private sector companies to eliminate the practice of racial discrimination; incorporation of the positive image of the Afro-Brazilian family into the education system and didactic and paradidactic literature, as well as the introduction of the history of African civilizations and the African in Brazil.

¹⁰Free translation (Own). Through compensatory and redistributive actions that compensate or correct the discrimination they have suffered throughout their lives. Based on this principle, it is argued that those who are different cannot be treated equally so as not to perpetuate inequalities.

7,824, of October 11, 2012 (Brasil, 2012b), which defined the conditions for the reservation of vacancies and established the transition of reservation of vacancies in public HEIs. From Normative Ordinance No. 18, of October 11, 2012, the basic concept for the application of the Law was established (Cavalcanti et al., 2019). According to article 2 of Decree No. 7,824, of October 11, 2012 (Brasil, 2012b),

As instituições federais vinculadas ao Ministério da Educação que ofertam vagas de educação superior reservarão, em cada concurso seletivo para ingresso nos cursos de graduação, por curso e turno, no mínimo cinquenta por cento de suas vagas para estudantes que tenham cursado integralmente o ensino médio em escolas públicas, [...], observadas as seguintes condições: I - o mínimo cinquenta por cento das vagas de que trata o caput serão reservadas a estudantes com renda familiar bruta igual ou inferior a um inteiro e cinco décimos salário-mínimo per capita ; e II - serão preenchidas, por curso e turno, por autodeclarados pretos, pardos e indígenas e por pessoas com deficiência, nos termos da legislação pertinente, em proporção ao total de vagas, no mínimo, igual à proporção respectiva de pretos, pardos, indígenas e pessoas com deficiência na população da unidade federativa onde está instalada a instituição, segundo o último censo da Fundação Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística – IBGE¹¹ (Brasil, 2012, s.p).

It can be seen that Law 12.711/2012 imposed that: "*um programa de cotas crescente em todas as universidades e institutos federais até atingir, em 2016, o nível de 50% das vagas em todos os cursos dedicados às cotas e padronizou os critérios para sua distribuição*" (Wainer; Melguizo, 2018, p. 3).¹² It was finally judged constitutionally unanimously by the ministers of the Federal Supreme Court (FSC) on April 26, 2012. This legislative framework is in harmony with that pointed out by Oliva and Beltrán (2020). For the authors,

Se considera el Derecho Internacional de los Derechos Humanos como un marco normativo para orientar el diseño, implementación,

¹¹Free translation (Own). Federal institutions linked to the Ministry of Education that offer higher education places will reserve, in each selection procedure for admission to undergraduate courses, by course and shift, at least fifty percent of their places for students who have fully attended high school in public schools, [...], subject to the following conditions: I - at least fifty percent of the places referred to in the caput will be reserved for students with a gross family income equal to or less than one integer and five tenths of a minimum wage per capita ; and II - will be filled, by course and shift, by self-declared black, brown and indigenous people and people with disabilities, under the terms of the relevant legislation, in a proportion to the total number of places, at least equal to the respective proportion of black, brown, indigenous and people with disabilities in the population of the federative unit where the institution is located, according to the last census of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics - BIGS (Brasil, 2012, s. p).

¹²Free translation (Own). An increasing quota program in all universities and federal institutes until reaching, in 2016, the level of 50% of the vacancies in all courses dedicated to quotas and standardizes the criteria for their distribution.

monitoreo y evaluación de políticas públicas, analizar los problemas sociales y las condiciones de desigualdad e identificar las distribuciones inequitativas de poder que dificultan el desarrollo”¹³ (Oliva; Beltrán, 2020, p. 2).

Figure 1 shows Law No. 12.711/2012 with its scope and configurations. The criteria have been established in a clearer and more aim way, valid for Federal Higher Education Institutions (FHEI). The figure shows that the first criterion is the application of 50% of places for students from public schools. This is followed by the racial criterion and finally income.

Figure 1 - Representation of Law No. 12.711/2012

Source: Ferreira (2020, p. 9).

The institutionalization of the reservation of places for students with disabilities was established by art. 3 of Law No. 13,409 of 28 December 2016 (Brasil, 2016),

Em cada instituição federal de educação superior, as vagas de que trata o art. 1º desta Lei serão preenchidas, por curso e turno, por autodeclarados pretos, pardos e indígenas e por pessoas com deficiência, nos termos da legislação, em proporção ao total de vagas no mínimo igual à proporção respectiva de pretos, pardos, indígenas e pessoas com deficiência na população da unidade da Federação onde está instalada a instituição, segundo o último censo da Fundação Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística – IBGE¹⁴ (Brasil, 2016, s.p).

¹³Free translation (Own). The International Law of the Human Rights as a normative framework to guide the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of public policies, analyze social problems and conditions of inequality and identify the inequitable distributions of power that hinder development.

¹⁴Free translation (Own). In each federal institution of higher education, the places referred to in art. 1 of this Law will be filled, by course and shift, by self-declared black, brown and indigenous people and

However, it would be relevant to note that the current legislation only contemplates people with disabilities from public schools. Outside this group, those who have disabilities, but study in private schools, with or without a scholarship, continue to compete with the others, without taking advantage of compensatory policies (Reis, 2022). Given the imprecision of the current legislation on this topic, the FHEI tended to adopt other legal documents, respecting the minimum value of the Quota Law in their notices, based on their administrative autonomy (Reis, 2022). The author draws attention to the fact that, "*por outro lado, a não padronização em escala nacional dos documentos a serem adotados pelas instituições pode denotar uma fragilidade, inclusive na própria garantia dos direitos dessa população*"¹⁵ (Cabral, 2018, p. 20).

The diagram in Figure 2 helps to understand this distribution of vacancy reservations.

Figure 2 - Distribution of vacancies in higher education as of Law No. 13,409/16

Source: Reis (2022, p. 122) adapted.

Through this diagram, it can be seen that branches were added in relation to the diagram in Figure 3 on page 48. The first criterion remained, 50% of vacancies for

people with disabilities, under the terms of the legislation, in a proportion to the total number of places at least equal to the respective proportion of black, brown, indigenous and people with disabilities in the population of the unit of the Federation where the institution is located, according to the last census of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics – BIGS.

¹⁵Free translation (Own). On the other hand, the non-standardization on a national scale of the documents to be adopted by the institutions may denote a fragility, including in the very guarantee of the rights of this population.

public schools. After applying the criteria of public school and per capita income less than or equal to 1.5 minimum wages, the criterion of the BBI group is applied, percentage of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (BIGS) referring to the Federation Unit (FU). Next, the criterion of people with disabilities is applied, a percentage of the BIGS referring to the FU.

Based on these notes, Reis (2022) argues that having access to higher education is not a concession or benefit offered by the State. The author reinforces that, in addition to access, it would be a duty, an obligation. In this sense, she points out that this right is fully guaranteed without stopping in a partisan political discourse.

Ansay (2015) and Januário (2019) argue that, in addition to legislation, it would be necessary and important to implement policies that enable the effective permanence of these students with disabilities and that can be the focus of surveillance by social movements and civil society (Reis, 2022).

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Senkevics and Mello (2022) present data, based on their studies, on the percentage distribution of public-school freshmen and black, brown, and indigenous (BBI) public school students in undergraduate courses at the Federal Institutions of Higher Education (FIHE). This distribution was made by HEI, course and shift in the country between 2012 and 2016 and demonstrates the heterogeneity of the student profile of higher education in the country from the Quota Law. Table 2 shows the evolution of the composition of the FIHE entrants by the categories of the Quota Law from 2012 to 2016.

Table 2 - Participation of groups benefiting from the Quota Law in FIHE in Brazil from 2012 to 2016 (%)

Year	Public School	Public School and BBI	Public School and income	Public School, BBI and income
2012	55,4	27,7	48,2	24,9
2013	56,7	29,9	48,6	26,8
2014	58,5	33,2	50,4	29,4
2015	62,2	34,4	52,0	29,9
2016	63,6	38,4	54,8	34,0

Source: Senkevics and Mello (2022, p. 213) adapted.

The data in this table indicate that there was a linear growth in the growth of all the groups of charities of the Quota Law from 2012 to 2016. Of these groups, public schools showed an average growth of 2.1% per year and a cumulative growth of 14.8% in the period considered.

Public schools and BBI, an average growth of 2.7% per year and a cumulative growth of 38.6% in the period considered. Public school and income, an average growth of 1.7% per year and a cumulative growth of 13.7% in the period considered. Finally, public school, BBI and income, an average growth of 2.3% per year and a cumulative of 36.5% in the period considered. Based on this more general data analysis, an analysis is carried out in only one HFES, but with a longer period. The FHEI chosen is the Federal Institute of Brasília (FIB) whose *Campi* are: Brasília, Ceilândia, Estrutural, Gama, Planaltina, Riacho Fundo, Samambaia, São Sebastião and Taguatinga.

The Table 3 shows the panorama by *Campus* in relation to the percentage of enrollment in the vacancy reservation modality from 2012 to 2021. This percentage is calculated by the ratio between the total enrollment in the year and the total enrollment in the vacancy reservation modality in the same year.

Table 3 – Percentage of enrollment in the modality of reservation of vacancies at FIB Campuses from 2012 to 2021

Percentage of enrollments in the vacancy reservation modality by <i>Campus</i> .									
Year	<i>Campus</i>								
	Bras.	Ceil.	Estrut.	Gama	Planalt.	R. Fundo	Sam.	S. Seb.	Taguat.
2012	18,10	0,00	0,00	11,35	12,59	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
2013	1,86	0,00	0,00	52,87	6,90	0,00	0,00	0,00	50,00
2014	18,16	0,00	0,00	20,60	23,14	53,57	0,00	38,71	52,25
2015	12,21	0,00	18,51	95,71	22,97	62,22	0,00	37,04	44,60
2016	0,00	0,00	29,23	57,75	29,52	55,43	0,00	42,86	40,27
2017	35,24	37,96	42,16	59,91	32,79	58,82	0,00	54,55	52,32
2018	43,41	50,00	39,74	56,30	36,91	54,01	18,31	49,83	52,39
2019	52,79	53,04	36,11	35,97	38,37	54,46	52,53	49,55	53,86
2020	52,18	52,85	35,84	51,53	41,07	55,12	40,72	41,63	53,24
2021	46,14	47,92	38,46	46,24	36,81	52,96	30,38	32,72	53,36

Source: prepared by the author based on data made available by NIESR (2021).

Table 3 shows that only from 2018 onwards all FIB *Campi* registered enrollments with reserved vacancies in higher education classes. In addition to this finding, it can be seen that the Riacho Fundo and Taguatinga *Campi* are the ones that

maintain a regularity in relation to the growth in the percentage of vacancy reservations at this level of education. Graph 1 shows the percentages of enrollments by reservation of vacancies in higher education in the period from 2014 to 2021.

Graph 1 – Percentage of enrollments by reservation of vacancies in higher education at the Taguatinga Campus

Source: prepared by the author based on data provided by NIESR (2021).

It can be seen from the graph that since the implementation of higher education in this *Campus*, the percentage of enrollments by reservation of vacancies has been close to 50%, although there have been drops in this percentage in the years 2015 and 2016. From then on, there was a slight oscillation in the percentage of enrollments by reservation of vacancies. However, the linearization curve points to a stabilization trend, around 53%, in the percentage of enrollments by reservation of vacancies in higher education at this *Campus*. It is verified that the number of enrollments in the ethnic/racial modality is higher than the others offered by reservation of vacancies. It is also noticed that the number of enrollments for people with disabilities (special needs) is shy in relation to BBI and income.

According to the 2021 higher education census, at the FIB Taguatinga *Campus*, 53.36% of enrollments are reserved for vacancies and there is at least one student in each of the categories indicated above (Inep, 2021). Thus, it is perceived that the profile of higher education students at the FIB Taguatinga *Campus* has a heterogeneous characteristic. This diversification of the profile of students at this *Campus* must be considered when considering the claim of uniqueness in higher education.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Although this work has been restricted to the analysis of the right to higher education of students from public schools, low-income, blacks, childbirth, indigenous and people with disabilities in line with Human Rights, only in a *Campus* of a Federal Institute, it does not deviate from a more general analysis of this theme. This means that the legislation implemented from 2012 onwards has formed a new panorama of higher education in the country. Over the course of a decade, affirmative action policies were consolidated, which diversified the profile of university students in Brazilian HEIs.

In this sense, the questions posed for this work: the legislative processes have corrected the historical debt with the population of students who were once excluded from higher education? In other words, through the current legislation, is the right to access, permanence and completion of higher education being guaranteed to these students? Would have as answers that, although there is a long way to go with regard to the right to higher education in Brazil, it can be seen that in the last two decades the right to higher education and Human Rights have gone hand in hand in the country. This was possible due to an intense and persistent struggle for affirmative action policies in the context of access to higher education for people who previously did not have access to this level of education.

In this way, it was possible to dialogue with the aim of this study, which consists of investigating the validity of the legislation in the correction of this historical debt with this population of students, with regard to the right to higher education. As already pointed out, I had its limits in the analysis of the population of higher education students of a *Campus* of a Federal Institute. Future studies could extend the analysis to a larger population of students, or carry out longitudinal studies on this topic, or even make comparisons with similar studies.

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